

Protocol for anonymizing data collected in scientific research: biomedical signals, videos, and qualitative data

Rodrigo Ortega Tierno
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0006-1692-7443

Wanghley Soares Martins
Pratt School of Engineering
Duke University
Durham, NC, USA
ORCID: 0000-0002-5110-4024

Luiza Maire David Luiz
Departamento de Fisioterapia
Faculdade Anhanguera de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-4630-6692

Fábio Henrique Monteiro Oliveira
Grupo de Pesquisa em Computação Aplicada
Instituto Federal de Brasília
Brasília - DF, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-0344-5801

Adriano de Oliveira Andrade
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-5689-6606

Abstract— Research in healthcare has been transformed by the growing complexity and richness of the data collected. Despite this, data sharing practices remain limited, and research shows that only a small proportion of published medical articles make their data publicly available. This gap compromises the scientific principles of reproducibility and replicability, which are essential for validating results and accelerating discoveries. Data collection and sharing face significant challenges, such as high costs, logistical difficulties, and problems in anonymizing sensitive data, especially biomedical signals. Several techniques have been developed to address these challenges. In this scenario, this work proposes a comprehensive method for anonymizing multi-modal biomedical data, integrating physiological signals, structured clinical data, and audiovisual content, with the work itself being a use case for the proposed method.

Keywords — *anonymization, Parkinson’s disease, biomedical signals, automation*

I. INTRODUCTION

Research in healthcare, specifically biomedical engineering and healthtech, generates increasingly rich and complex data - combining the growing availability of data and computational advances - often combining different modalities of information on the same participant. A single study can collect biomedical signals (such as electrocardiograms), qualitative data (such as interview transcripts or follow-up sheets) and audiovisual records. However, in an analysis of more than 7,750 published medical articles, only 9% of those published from 2015-2020 said they made the data publicly available, but only 3% actually shared it [1].

In the scientific method, the principles of reproducibility - the ability to redo the analysis with the same data - and replicability - the ability to recreate the study independently and obtain consistent results - are invaluable [2]. They function as a quality control mechanism intrinsic to science, ensuring that the conclusions published are reliable and not the result of error, chance or bias. Furthermore, by allowing the scientific community to build on previous work, they accelerate the advancement of knowledge. However, the

practical application of these principles is entirely dependent on open access to raw data and research metadata. When the data is not shared, the study becomes a “black box”, whose results must be accepted on faith rather than verification [2]. Therefore, the practice of making data available is not just a complement, but an act that actively reinforces the integrity, seriousness and credibility of scientific work.

Furthermore, research in human health is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by the need for faster and more transparent responses. As part of the Open Science movement (*Open Science*) [3], the Open Data culture (*Open Data*) has emerged as one of its most important pillars [4]. Far from being a passing trend, it is consolidating itself as a powerful mechanism, capable of significantly accelerating the pace of scientific discoveries [5].

Data collection is widely recognized as one of the most challenging aspects of scientific research, facing a series of obstacles that can compromise both the quality and integrity of the studies conducted [6] [7]. These challenges stem from a set of interdependent variables, which include the high costs associated with materials and equipment, time constraints, logistical complexities, low availability of participants and, especially, difficulties in locating and recruiting individuals belonging to the desired target group.

The anonymization of biomedical signals, such as electrocardiogram (ECG) or electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, is particularly challenging [6]. Current approaches in the literature include clustering-based techniques (*clustering*), which seek to generalize quasi-identifiers; the addition of noise to the data to increase the variety between equivalence classes (as in the θ -sensitive proposal); and the use of artificial intelligence to automate the de-identification process [8]. Statistical methods, such as the dynamic separatrix approach (DAS), attempt to optimize generalization by dynamically defining the optimal number of groups, with the promise of low computational cost [8].

The literature on data anonymization demonstrates a rapidly evolving field in which several attempts and techniques have been developed to address various privacy challenges in different domains [9–11]. The studies

range from the anonymization of mobile sensor data using deep autoencoders that have achieved activity recognition accuracy above 92% and reduced user identification to less than 7% [12], to the anonymization of biomedical data employing scalable algorithms such as genetic approaches and greedy top-down methods for high-dimensional datasets with hundreds of attributes [13].

With regards to privacy, K-anonymity and its variants have been extensively tested with clustering-based partitioning methods and hybrid approaches that combine multiple privacy models [14], while differential privacy techniques have evolved to include synthetic data generation using large language models and adversarial training mechanisms [15]. Recent work has also explored information theory approaches for mobile motion sensors that reduce user traceability by 60% while keeping utility loss below 0.5 Mean Absolute Error [16], adversarial autoencoder methods that protect sensitive attributes such as gender and identity in voice biometrics and collaborative object detection, and privacy-preserving frameworks for continuous data publishing that handle streaming location data and time-series information. These diverse tests collectively illustrate the progression of the field, from simple suppression and generalization techniques to sophisticated machine learning techniques [10, 17].

In this context, the aim of this work is to propose a comprehensive method for anonymizing multi-modal biomedical data, including physiological signals, datasets with structured clinical data and audiovisual content, by developing an integrated strategy that enables secure scientific collaboration and rigorously preserves the privacy of participants in clinical studies. This approach aims to establish a technological *framework* that facilitates the responsible sharing of research data between institutions, ensuring regulatory compliance with personal data protection guidelines while maintaining the scientific usefulness of the data for secondary analysis and validation of results, thus contributing to the advancement of collaborative clinical research.

II. METHOD

This work was motivated by the need to analyze, organize, and anonymize data from the research project “Data analysis and machine learning techniques as a tool to aid in the detection and characterization of Parkinson’s disease” (CAAE 77752723.9.0000.5152), which consists of raw signals from inertial and capacitive sensors resulting from work [18], referring to the execution of specific movements performed by a group of subjects, classified as people affected by Parkinson’s disease (PD) and with motor symptoms, and neurologically healthy individuals. In addition to the sensor signals, spreadsheets with qualitative data from participants, clinical data, and videos of the collections are part of the data set.

In order to make the processing of this data fast and scalable, scripts were developed to anonymize it automatically. The original organization of the data used the names of the participants to identify folders and files resulting from the collections.

A. Data to be anonymized

This section describes how the original research data was organized and which information needed to be anonymized.

2.1.1 Qualitative spreadsheet

Excel spreadsheet organized into two sheets, one for each group: Healthy and Parkinson’s patients. Both sheets contain information about the participants’ identity, such as name and date of birth, and other data about the participant’s characteristics, such as the limb evaluated (e.g., right or left hand), the date of collection, and the date of the UPDRS assessment if the participant is in the Parkinson’s group.

2.1.2 MDS-UPDRS

The Movement Disorder Society–Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) assessment carried out with participants in the Parkinson’s group was also made available in Excel spreadsheet format. This spreadsheet contains the results of the assessment of items in parts 2 and 3 of the scale, referring to the motor signs of Parkinson’s disease, as well as the date of the assessment, the initials of the therapists who performed the assessment, the version of the scale used in the assessment, the results of the tremor scores, and the participant’s identification (i.e., ID and name).

2.1.3 Collected signals

This data was organized into a set of folders as illustrated in Figure 1. In this case, the only personal information about each participant that allowed their identification was their names, which identified the folders and files resulting from their collections. The files were named as follows: participant-name_repetition-number_member-evaluated.csv, with the right hand identified by the letter “r” and the left hand by the letter ‘l’ (e.g., “someone-name_01_r.csv”).

Fig. 1. Tree diagram of the organization of the data collected in the activities with inertial sensor sets (i.e., tremsem) and non-contact capacitive sensors (i.e., plessey). The v01_name folders correspond to the participant’s ID, ranging from v01 to v30 in both groups, and the participant’s personal name, information that must be omitted in the data anonymization process for publishing. Source: original research results.

2.1.4 Media

The media related to the recording of collection activities are important materials for understanding the method used, allowing us to observe how the collections were organized, the orientation of the activities, and to visualize the characteristics of each group of participants.

This stage of anonymization was challenging, as there were more than 250 videos, without any labels identifying the participant or metadata that could be used to verify the time of collection, as well as being between 2:30 and 4 minutes long each. The videos were thoroughly analyzed following the following protocol:

Initial analysis: With the aim of identifying participants for subsequent editing and organization in the new directory.

Thorough analysis: The videos were watched again, this time taking notes to establish the criteria for editing the videos. The main observations made were:

- Marking of the start and end times for collections;
- Marking of the seconds during which the name of the respective volunteer was said during the collection;
- Whether the participant's face appears at any point in the recording.

Video editing criteria: Based on the markings, the following criteria were defined to facilitate decision-making when editing the videos:

- If the participant's face and/or name was only mentioned before and/or after the collection activities, the video can simply be cut;
- If the participant's name was mentioned during the collection activities, then the video should be muted for the seconds in which the name was identified;
- If the participant's face appeared during collection, then the video must be edited with a blur to hide the participant's identity.

B. Anonymization

This section details how each piece of data mentioned in the previous section was anonymized. This work is part of a project approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlândia (CEP-UFU) (CAAE 77752723.9.0000.5152) and, therefore, it was necessary to collect the signatures of the participants of the research that originated the data in order to obtain authorization for its disclosure. The collection of signatures was controlled in a private Google Sheets spreadsheet, which served as a parameter in the anonymization scripts, so that only the data of participants who signed the informed consent form (ICF) were analyzed and anonymized for publication, while those who did not sign were left out of this work.

2.2.1 Spreadsheet editing scripts

The scripts were developed in Python, and the pandas library was used to edit the qualitative and UPDRS spreadsheets, omitting columns with sensitive information and columns that were considered irrelevant for analysis in subsequent studies (e.g., blank columns or columns with superficial observations). New columns were also created, such as age at the time of collection and global ID of participants.

Regarding the files containing sensor signal data, a script was developed to copy the files to a new folder with the same organization, but omitting the names of the participants from the file identifications. For this purpose, the naming protocol illustrated in Figure 2 was used.

Fig. 2. File naming protocol. A) Volunteer ID; B) Volunteer group, where DP - Parkinson's patients and GC - Control group (healthy individuals); C) Type of sensor to which that signal refers (i.e., Plessey or TremSen); D) Repetition of collection activities; E) evaluated limb, where ME - left hand and MD - right hand; and F) file extension (e.g., .edf, .csv, .log, .mov, .mp4, etc.). Source: original research results.

2.2.2 Video editing

After the audiovisual analysis of the videos, a spreadsheet was prepared with all the markings of which moments should be cut and muted, and which videos should have blur applied. Since manual editing is a time-consuming process, and given the volume of videos, the FFMPEG tool was used to perform the editing via command prompt. Combined with this tool, a simple Python script was also implemented to scan the entire media directory and apply the edits indicated in the spreadsheet.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Once the file naming protocol, video editing criteria, and data organization criteria had been defined, the original data underwent the anonymization process described in the methods section. Even so, manual adjustments were made to ensure the integrity of the data and the volunteers to whom it belonged.

The data relating to the sensor signals were published in a private repository on Zenodo [19]. An ethical commitment agreement was also drawn up, so that those interested in using the data for research purposes only would be granted access, in accordance with the laws and ethical standards governing research involving human subjects.

Anonymizing the videos was a challenge due to their high volume and the need for manual work to mark the adjustment periods in each video. Despite this, a script was developed using the FFMPEG editing tool to automate video editing based on the annotations made.

As future work, the publication of properly edited and anonymized videos is planned. For this stage to be completed, only the application of blurring to the participants' faces remains pending.

IV. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

A. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest in the ethical sphere.

B. Statement of informed Consent

All data used in this study were provided after participants signed informed consent forms (ICF) for the project approved by the CEP-UFU (CAAE 77752723.9.0000.5152).

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the principle that knowledge is a common good, the data used in this research that does not allow for the identification of participants will be shared publicly. The data is being made available so that other researchers can also contribute to the development of new technologies to improve the quality of life of individuals with Parkinson's disease.

This paper proposes methods and protocols used in a real project approved by CEP-UFU, which can be used in any context where there is a need to anonymize sensitive information from research involving human subjects. As a result, the findings of this research will be published while still preserving the identities of the participants.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work was carried out with the support of the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (444437/2024-0, 442150/2023-7, and 405365/2023-3), Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), Foundation for Research Support of the State of Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG APQ-05015-24), Foundation for Research Support of the Federal District (FAPDF, Call No. 09/2023 - Spontaneous Demand, Process No. 00193-00002192/2023-37). AOA (302942/2022-0) is fellow of CNPq.

- [1] J. Kaiser and J. Brainard, "Ready, set, share: Researchers brace for new data-sharing rules," *Science*, vol. 379, pp. 322–325, Jan. 2023.
- [2] T. Miyakawa, "No raw data, no science: another possible source of the reproducibility crisis," *Molecular Brain*, vol. 13, p. 24, Feb. 2020.
- [3] R. T. Thibault, O. B. Amaral, F. Argolo, A. E. Bandrowski, D. Alexandra R, and N. I. Drude, "Open Science 2.0: Towards a truly collaborative research ecosystem," *PLoS Biol.*, vol. 21, p. e3002362, Oct. 2023.
- [4] S. Ghai, R. Thériault, P. Forscher, Y. Shoda, M. Syed, A. Puthillam, H. C. Peng, D. Basnight-Brown, A. Majid, F. Azevedo, and L. Singh, "A manifesto for a globally diverse, equitable, and inclusive open science," *Commun. Psychol.*, vol. 3, pp. 1–9, Jan. 2025.
- [5] H. Numajiri and T. Hayashi, "Analysis on open data as a foundation for data-driven research," *Scientometrics*, vol. 129, pp. 6315–6332, Oct. 2024.
- [6] T. Meurers, K. Otte, H. Abu Attieh, F. Briki, J. Despraz, M. Halilovic, B. Kaabachi, V. Milicevic, A. Müller, G. Papapostolou, F. N. Wirth, J. L. Raisaro, and F. Prasser, "A quantitative analysis of the use of anonymization in biomedical research," May 2025.
- [7] R. J. Holden, A. M. M. Scott, P. L. T. Hoonakker, A. S. Hundt, and P. Carayon, "Data collection challenges in community settings: Insights from two field studies of patients with chronic disease," *Quality of life research : an international journal of quality of life aspects of treatment, care and rehabilitation*, vol. 24, p. 1043, Aug. 2014.
- [8] K. Coelho, M. Okuyama, M. Nogueira, A. Vieira, E. Silva, and J. Nacif, "Uma abordagem dinâmica para anonimização de dados de saúde por separatrizes," in *Anais do XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos*, (Porto Alegre, RS, Brasil), pp. 826–839, SBC, 2024.
- [9] B. C. M. Fung, K. Wang, R. Chen, and P. S. Yu, "Privacy-preserving data publishing: A survey of recent developments," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 42, June 2010.
- [10] B.-C. Chen, D. Kifer, K. LeFevre, and A. Machanavajjhala, "Privacy-Preserving Data Publishing," *DBS*, vol. 2, pp. 1–167, Oct. 2009.
- [11] W. Lin, J. Qian, W. Liu, and L. Wu, "A Summary of Privacy-Preserving Data Publishing in the Local Setting," *arXiv*, Dec. 2023.
- [12] M. Malekzadeh, R. G. Clegg, A. Cavallaro, and H. Haddadi, "Mobile sensor data anonymization," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Internet of Things Design and Implementation, IoTDI '19*, (New York, NY, USA), p. 49–58, Association for Computing Machinery, 2019.

- [13] T. Meurers, R. Bild, K.-M. Do, and F. Prasser, "A scalable software solution for anonymizing high-dimensional biomedical data," *GigaScience*, vol. 10, p. giab068., Oct. 2021.
- [14] A. Majeed and S. Lee, "Anonymization techniques for privacy preserving data publishing: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 8512–8545, 2021.
- [15] K. Amin, A. Bie, W. Kong, A. Kurakin, N. Ponomareva, U. Syed, A. Terzis, and S. Vassilvitskii, "Private prediction for large-scale synthetic text generation," *arXiv*, July 2024.
- [16] R. Masood, W. Y. Cheng, D. Vatsalan, D. Mishra, H. J. Asghar, and M. A. Kaafar, "Privacy Preserving Release of Mobile Sensor Data," *arXiv*, May 2022.
- [17] Z. Zuo, M. Watson, D. Budgen, R. Hall, C. Kennelly, and N. Al Moubayed, "Data Anonymization for Pervasive Health Care: Systematic Literature Mapping Study," Oct. 2021.
- [18] F. H. Monteiro Oliveira, D. Fernandes da Cunha, A. Gomes Rabelo, L. M. David Luiz, M. Fraga Vieira, A. Alves Pereira, and A. de Oliveira Andrade, "A non-contact system for the assessment of hand motor tasks in people with parkinson's disease ," 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-04001-5>.
- [19] F. H. M. Oliveira, R. Ortega Tierno, and A. de Oliveira Andrade, "Base de dados sobre o uso de sensores capacitivos sem contato para caracterização de movimento de pessoas com Parkinson." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15975202>, 2025. [Data set]. Zenodo.